

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Introductory Technology as it Impacts Modern Society in the World (Nigeria as a Case Study)

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Received: 01 January, 2022
Accepted: 12 February, 2022
Published: 15 February, 2022

Abstract

Technology may be defined as the tangible and immaterial things created either by application or mental and physical work in order to achieve a goal. Technological education, from the other side, does not concentrate on a certain job path but rather on providing fundamental technical skills. As a result, while all technical education programmes are technical in nature, not all technical education programmes are vocational in nature. This subtle relationship explains the interchangeable usage of both names in scholarly literature. According to Nigeria's national education plan, technical education is focused on the development of highly technological human resources with the goal of producing a national pool of skilled and self-sufficient artisans, technicians, including technicians in technical and vocational fields. Education is just a "par excellent" tool for national development in the world. Non-governmental groups, communities, and people have all actively participated, as has the government. As a result, it is vital for the country to articulate clearly and unequivocally the philosophy and aims that motivate its investment in education. That was what the National Education Policy wants to achieve. According to the study's findings, one of most endemic difficulties militating against participants' performance throughout introductory Technology are really a lack of training infrastructure, a shortage of teaching staff, insufficient discovering, a vast curriculum, poor appreciation and compensation, as well as inefficient guardian and counseling center.

Keywords: Technical; Material; Introductory

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1. Introduction

Technology is a collection of techniques, skills, methods, and processes that are used in the production of products and services, or the pursuit of objectives like scientific research. Technology can be described also as knowledge of procedures, processes, and such, or it can be encoded in machines that allow them to be operated without a complete grasp of how they function. The most fundamental type of technology is the creation and usage of fundamental tools. The Neolithic Revolution and the prehistoric discovery about how to manage fire increased food availability, and the invention of the wheel made it simpler for humans to move and control their environment. The printing press, the telephone, and the Internet are examples of historical developments that have reduced physical barriers to communication and allowed humans to engage freely on a worldwide scale. There are numerous effects of technology. It has fostered the emergence of the leisure class and the development of much more contemporary

economies (particularly today's global economy). Many technological processes produce undesirable by-products, like pollution, and resource depletion, both of which impair the Earth's environment. Innovations always had an influence on a social standards and have resulted in new ethical issues. Only two examples are the creation of the notion of efficiency of human production and questions of bioethics. Philosophical debates have emerged on use of technology, including disagreements over whether it improves or exacerbates human conditions. Neo-Luddism, anarcho-primitivism, and other reactionary movements decry technology's pervasiveness, claiming that it harms the environment and alienates people; proponents of transhumanism and techno-progressivism, on the other hand, see continued technological progress as beneficial to society and the human condition (Liddell et al, 1980).

Technical education, on either hand, facilitates the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. Technical and